

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Tackling the school attendance crisis

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for improving school attendance

[CotN_Attendance_Report_10.pdf](#)

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **There is a crisis in school attendance.** In the past eight years absence rates have increased by 57%.
- **The crisis has hit the most disadvantaged children hardest.** Children on free school meals, carers and those on an Education and Health Care Plan have the highest non-attendance rates.
- **Life chances are blighted**, and the cost is not just to individuals and families but to the wider economy and society.
- **National level focus:**
 - Create systems that support early intervention and inclusive school environments through frameworks such as Ofsted.
 - Build effective joining up of services.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Establish early screening methods in school to identify at risk children.
 - Develop inclusive school practices.
 - Create local partnerships to provide integrated supports, target support to individuals, families and local context.
 - Build on approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: School absence rates have soared in the past few years and especially since the pandemic

This has long term impacts on life chances and costs the wider economy and society. The most deprived and vulnerable children are most at risk. They have have complex support needs that need addressing.

In 2023-2024, One in five school children are persistently absent

For children from disadvantage backgrounds or on free school meals, almost two in five were persistently absent

For carers of those on an Education Health Care Plan almost two in five were persistently absent

In the past 8 years, school absence rates have risen by 57%

150,000 children are absent from school for half or more of the academic year Maths.

In 2018/19 only 36% of children who were persistently absent achieved expected grades in English and Maths compared to 78% of children who were not persistently absent. Persistently absent children are nearly four times as likely to become NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training)

What you can do at a local level

- **Develop early identification systems in schools** to identify and support those most at risk
- **Develop inclusive school practices** through individually tailored support, close links with families, curricula which engage, enrichment activities
- **Target approaches to individual, family and local contexts.** The range of factors that lead to non attendance need recognising and addressing.
- **Build local partnerships** between education, healthcare and social services to support the needs of individuals and families.
- **Build on the kinds of local programmes highlighted below.**

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Barriers to Education Project	Established between a UK autistic charity and regional Educational Psychology Advisory Group. A multi-agency project group was set up and through a coproduction process, developed the WARMTH Framework, which identifies six key foundations to reduce barriers to education and supports development of a tiered approach to support.	Provision of services tailored to meeting support needs of neurodiverse children and their families, lead to more inclusive school practices and improve attendance.
The EWO Project	Collaboration between Suffolk Psychology and Therapeutic Services (P&TS) and Suffolk's statutory attendance service. Focuses on supporting CYP with barriers to education and attendance - understood to be complex and highly individual, in some cases related to unmet special educational needs. The project aims to promote effective multi-agency working.	Effective multi agency working between services and families to provide better support, improve attendance and meet needs.
Bradford SAFE Taskforce	Aims to leverage schools' leadership, facilities, and local networks to deliver timely and effective support to children vulnerable to violence. A range of programmes e.g. gender specific mentoring schemes; attendance intervention based on whole child approach includes interventions assisting with transport and liaising with both school and careers to bridge the gap between home and school. a character education programme aimed at developing children's social and emotional skills.	Improved children's attendance, behaviour, and engagement with their education. Also reduction in the number of suspensions and permanent exclusions.
North Birkenhead Cradle to Career Attendance Pilot	Adopts a localised panel approach to addressing complex cases individually by improving cross sector communications around specific attendance barriers, improving holistic support for children and families; understanding root causes and developing medium to long term support plans.	Improved attendance; support for children and families; cross sector communication; understanding of barriers to attendance.
Supporting CYP with severe attendance difficulties	Psychoeducational resources teach an individual about their condition by providing support, information, and management skills,	Appropriate support provided in a supportive and inclusive environment.
Alternative Education: The R place pilot	A pilot project for students aged 13-16 excluded or at risk of exclusion from mainstream school. Offers small group support based on nurture group principles (see The Six Principles of Nurture - nurtureuk). This offers a customised and tailored curriculum and safe and supportive environment within the Alternative Provision setting.	Improved engagement, attendance and achievement through meeting complex needs.